

A STUDY OF THE HISTOLOGICAL CHANGES INDURED BY SUBACUTE RESTRAINT ON WISTAR ALBINO RATS MASSED WITH EUGENOL EXTRACT

Dr. Pandian M¹, Dr. Rakesh Kumar², Srivalli M.^{3*}

^{1&3} Department of Physiology, Zydus Medical College & Hospital, Dahod, GJ, IND.

² Department of Anatomy, Zydus Medical College & Hospital, Dahod, GJ, IND.

Background- Essential oils derived from plants are widely utilised in the food and perfume industries as flavouring agents and fragrances, respectively. Traditional flora used to treat maladies, according to the World Health Organisation, require additional scientific research into their toxic adverse effects. **Objective:** - the aim of the study was to study the effect of 2-METHOXY-4-(PROP-2-EN-1-YL) PHENOL (EUGENOL) on histological ultra-changes and relative parameters in restraint stress induced female Wistar rats was studied. **Methods:-** A total of thirty Wistar albino female rats, weighing between 100-160g, were utilized in the study. The rats were categorized into five groups: group one served as the control group (unstressed and untreated), Group II served as the positive control (received only Polyglycerol {PG}), Group III was treated solely with Eugenol (150 mg/kg b.w.), Group IV experienced restraint stress alone, and Group V was treated with Eugenol and restraint stress (150 mg/kg b.w.). The duration of the treatment spanned across a period of 15 days. The histology and relative parameters research were measured on the 15th day. **Results-** Harris hematoxylin staining of the brain, liver, and renal cortex of rats given eugenol showed a relatively normal histological structure of the hepatic parenchyma. Examining the group III, IV & V subacute restraint stress rats were treated with eugenol, few isolated regions of hepatic parenchyma and certain renal tubules showed degenerative conditions. The flattened epithelial lining of several convoluted tubules seemed irregularly dilated. The hyaline substance and cellular casts occupied their lumina. Furthermore seen were thickened renal tubule basement membranes with a broken brush border. In addition, this eugenol-treated group showed signs of severe fibrosis in the renal interstitium and hepatic parenchyma. **Conclusion-** The examined essential oils did not exhibit noteworthy deleterious impacts on the brain, liver, and renal cortex of Wistar albino female rats. However, it is worth noting that the dimethoate, an organophosphorus insecticide, may induce substantial hepatotoxic and nephrotoxic effects in the remaining oils. Additional research encompassing a broader range of animal subjects and examining additional biochemical targets, including gender disparities, time course, dose response, blood chemistry, and time course, is imperative before endorsing the application of any of these compounds as insecticides.

Key words: Eugenol, Histology of Brain, Liver, Kidney, Wistar Albino Rats.

*To whom correspondence should be addressed. Ms. Srivalli M., Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, Zydus Medical College and Hospital, Dahod, GJ, IND.

I. INTRODUCTION

Drugs have traditionally come largely from plants. Many people worldwide, particularly those living in developing nations, rely on medicinal plants as an alternative or complementing form of treatment for a variety of illnesses. Using crude plant extracts, which might include a wide range of chemicals with frequently unknown biological effects, is one of the most widespread methods.[1] For the reason that medicinal plants are used without thinking about their possible harmful or poisonous impacts, the World Health Organisation says that traditional medicines made from these plants should have their poisonous effects studied more by scientists.[2] Essential oils have been used for a long time because of their biological effects, such as their ability to clean, relieve pain, calm, reduce inflammation, stop spasms, and numb the area.[3] Moreover, their stimulating or sedative effects are used in aromatherapy to boost wellness. [4–6]

Plant essential oils are naturally occurring compounds that are frequently in charge of giving a plant its particular flavor or aroma. As a result, these oils are widely used in both the food and perfume industries as flavoring agents and scents. [7–9] These oils are usually quite complex in composition and are made up of the volatile components found in the plants, which sets them apart from "fixed oils." Higher plants contain roughly 17,500 different types of aromatic chemicals.[8,9] Essential oils build up in many kinds of vegetative organs, including rhizomes [ginger, turmeric), barks (cinnamon), woods (rosewood, sandal wood), flowers (bergamot tree and tuberose), leaves (citronella, eucalyptus), and seeds (nutmeg). The majority of the time, it is still unclear how essential oils act biologically. That is plausible, but they have an ecological function. For instance, it has been discovered that numerous plant essential oil monoterpenoids have insecticidal activity in addition to being attractant, repellent, feeding deterrent, ovipositional stimulant, and able to alter behaviour towards different insect species.[8,10–12] Hydro distillation is a simple method for extracting the essential oil from *Cinnamomum* species.[13] For generations, the culinary industries have utilised oil extensively as a flavouring ingredient and additive.

A wide range of insect species are neurotoxic to the monoterpenoids found in plant essential oils. It has been demonstrated that they inhibit acetylcholinesterase (AChE), which is isolated from various bovine erythrocytes, and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) receptors in marine algae.[14,15] A prior study documented the involvement of a specific G-protein coupled receptor cascade in the mechanism of action of a particular plant essential oil. On the basis of the historical utilisation records of particular plant essential oils, conjecture has it that these oils may offer a favorable safety profile in relation to mammalian species. For instance, cinnamic aldehyde and eugenol have been utilised as flavoring agents in the food and fragrance industries, respectively, and eugenol is on the USFDA-GRAS (Generally Regarded as Safe) List. Hence, the primary objective of the present investigation was to determine whether or not these specific plant essential oils elicit detrimental effects on the liver and kidneys of laboratory animals.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study obtained approval from both the Institute's Animal Ethical Committee (IAEC number. 01/17/2015) and the Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CPCSEA). The experimental subjects consisted of healthy adult female albino rats of the Wistar breed, with a weight range of 150 – 220 g. All animal experiments conducted for the purpose of this project followed institutional and national standards for the preservation of animal welfare.

A. EXPERIMENTAL GROUPS

The animals were allocated into five groups, with six animals in each group, in a random manner. Sigma supplied the eugenol (2-methyl-4-[2-propenyl] phenol ($C_{10}H_{12}O_2$) compound.

Group I: This group of rats served as control.

Group II: Rats of this group were administrated with vehicle (PG) IP for 15 days.

Group III: Animals were administrated with Eugenol (150 mg/kg/day, IP for 15 consecutive days)

Group IV: Subjected to immobilization stress alone for 15 days (6 hr/day) and immobilization stress induced changes were observed in this group.

Group V: Animals were treated with Eugenol 150 mg/kg.b.wt along with immobilization stress for 15 days.

Every animal was sacrificed by decapitation under anesthesia on the sixteenth day. Following that, their brain, liver, and kidney were expeditiously procured, dissected, and portioned into 0.5 cm³ volumes. Subsequently, the sections were sectioned into 5-6 μ paraffin sections and subjected to staining in accordance with the methodology outlined by Drury and Wilington [18]. 1- Routine standard H&E stain to examine the cellular composition of the brain liver and kidney.

B. CORTICOSTERONE ANALYSIS

This procedure was conducted with minor alterations from the study conducted by Singh and Verman in 2008.[16] It relies on the oxidation of corticosteroids using ferric iron (III) in an acidic solution, followed by the formation of a complex with ferrous iron (II) and potassium hexacyanoferrate. 0.5 μ l of Plasma samples were combined with suitable volumes of corticosterone working solutions and transferred into a set of 10 ml volumetric flasks. Sulphuric acid (4N, 2ml) and ferric chloride (0.5%, 2 ml) were separately added, followed by the addition of potassium hexacyanoferrate (III) solution (0.5%, 0.5 ml).

The solution was subjected to heat in a water-bath, which was kept at a constant temperature of $70 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, for a duration of 30 minutes. The solution was intermittently agitated throughout this process. Afterward, the solution was diluted with distilled water until it reached the 5ml mark. The measurement of absorbance was conducted at a wavelength of 780 nm relative to the reagent blank.

C. PROCEDURE FOR INDUCING IMMOBILISATION STRESS

The rats were exposed to restraint stress by being placed in a wire mesh restrainer (Fig. 1) for a duration of 6 hours per day for a period of 15 days. The wire mesh restrainer consisted of a hardwood base with a hinged stainless steel wire mesh restrainer attached to it. The restrainer,

measuring 8cm in length, 4cm in width, and 4cm in height, was utilised for the trials. A padlock and latch were used to secure the rat in the restrainer.

D. STATISTICAL EVALUATION

Analysis of the data was done with the Windows statistical software package SPSS 10.0. Statistical analysis was carried out via Tukey's multiple comparison tests and ANOVA. Statistically significant was defined as $P < 0.05$.

III. RESULTS

A. CHANGES IN THE LEVELS OF CORTICOSTERONE

The levels of plasma corticosterone were assessed in every experimental group. Plasma corticosterone levels were considerably elevated in the stress group in comparison to the control and treated groups. In contrast, the stress-treated group with eugenol exhibits a statistically significant reduction ($p < 0.05$) in comparison to the stress-only group. This suggests that eugenol possesses anti-stress properties (Fig 1).

Fig. 1: Effect of Plasma corticosterone on restraint stress induced animals. Values are expressed as Mean $\pm$ SD, N=6.*compared with saline control; @compared with stress. The symbols represent statistical significance: *, @ < P 0.05.

B. HEMATOXYLIN AND EOSIN STAINING OF THE LIVER

The liver parenchyma of the control animals (group I and II) exhibited a typical arrangement of hepatocytes forming interconnected cords that extend from the central veins. These cords enclose the sinusoidal gaps, which are lined by endothelial cells and Von Kupffer cells. The hepatocytes exhibited a polyhedral shape, with cytoplasm that had a granular eosinophilic appearance. The nuclei of the hepatocytes were spherical and contained conspicuous nucleoli. A portion of them exhibited binucleation. Portal regions were observed at the corners of the lobules (Fig 1a, b). The analysis of the sample taken from animals treated with eugenol via intravenous route (group III) showed a liver parenchyma pattern that was nearly identical to the normal control (Fig 1c, d). The liver examination of animals that were intravenously treated with eugenol (group III) showed that the majority of the investigated specimens had a fairly normal structure of the liver tissue. Certain regions displayed a largely typical arrangement of liver cells, whereas others showed enlarged gaps between blood vessels and scattered patches of disrupted liver cell organisation. The observed region displayed hepatocytes with blurred borders and an atypical nuclear pattern (Fig 1e, f).

The animals in Group V, who were subjected to eugenol treatment and subacute restraint stress, exhibited an obvious affection of the hepatic parenchyma, as evidenced by the distinctive hepatic zonation observed in the collected liver tissues. The periportal areas exhibited hypertrophic cords of hyperchromatic cells with homogeneous cytoplasm and blurred demarcations. The nuclei exhibited a decreased size and a compact chromatin arrangement. The perivenous area exhibited fully deteriorated cells with condensed nuclei and cytoplasm filled with vacuoles. These cells were surrounded by a dense infiltration of neutrophils and lymphocytes, together with an elevated presence of Von Kupffer cells (Fig 2 a,b,c).

Fig 1:- Liver tissue sample stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) stain.

G I- Control Liver-100x

G II- PG Liver-100x

G III- TA-150mg-Liver-100x

G III- TA-150mg-Liver-400x

G IV- SA Liver-100x

G IV- SA Liver-400x

H&E staining of the liver segment is shown in Fig 1. (a) Hepatocyte anastomosing plates stained at 100X magnification of a control mouse liver segment, with the central veins denoted by "cv" as their sources. The letter "p" designates portal sections. The rat liver hepatocytes displaying a centrally placed, rounded, vesicular nucleus with a conspicuous nucleolus and eosinophilic cytoplasm (arrow). A portion of them have binucleated heads (arrows). K: Von Kupffer cell; E: endothelial cell; S: blood sinusoids. (b) A 100X magnification of the group IV section stain after eugenol treatment shows a virtually typical array of hepatocytes surrounding the central veins (cv). There are dilated sinusoidal spaces (s) in some places. Some cells have poorly defined nuclei (arrows) and are matted together. (c) A liver segment stained at 100X magnification displays freely anastomosing plates of almost normal hepatocytes, which limits the sinusoidal gaps. (d) Liver segment stain at 400X magnification for group III. (e) Section stain from group IV at 100X magnification, showing the hepatic lobules' almost intact structure. (f) Section stain from group IV magnified 400 times, revealing many granular Von Kupffer cells (K) and a small number of cells with vacuolated cytoplasm (*).

Fig 2:- Liver tissue sample stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) stain.

G V- TS-150mg-Liver-100x

G V- TS-150mg-Liver-100x

G V- TS-150mg-Liver-100x

Fig 2 (a-c): Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) stained liver segment from a wistar albino rat in group V that was treated with eugenol (150mg/kg/day). (a & b) A 100X magnification image showing portions of the portal area with a congested branch of the portal vein (v) surrounded by infiltration of mononuclear cells (arrowhead). Observe the clear division of the liver cells into zones; the liver cells near the portal area are strongly stained with eosin (farrow), whereas the cells near the central vein are deteriorated, contracted, and have condensed nuclei (*). (c) A 400X magnification image shows the architectural loss of hepatocytes, which are usually enlarged with nuclei situated off-center (shown by an arrow). These nuclei are displaced by clearly defined vacuoles within the cytoplasm (indicated by an arrowhead). There are sections of thicker plates consisting of extremely eosinophilic hepatocytes (shown by arrows). These hepatocytes have a glassy and uniform appearance, and their cell borders are not well defined. The intervening area (*) has many hepatocytes with a moth-eaten appearance, encircled by a dense infiltration of neutrophils (N) and lymphocytes (L). Additionally, there is an observed presence of hepatocytes that are clumped together and have eosinophilic characteristics (shown

by the double arrow). The presence of a higher quantity of Von Kupffer cells (K) together with a widespread infiltration of neutrophils (N) and lymphocytes (L) is also shown.

C. KIDNEY: HEMATOXYLIN AND EOSIN STAIN

An analysis of the kidney obtained from a control Wistar albino rat unveiled the characteristic architecture and structure of cortical tissue, including renal corpuscles that were clearly defined, as well as proximal and distal convoluted tubules (Fig 3a, b). Animals given vehicle alone (group II) showed no histological alterations, as seen by the almost control picture (Fig 3c, d). But in-group IV showed some peritubular and pericorpuscular cellular infiltration, which might be the result of subacute restraint stress (Fig 3g, h). Few kidney tubules also have deteriorated cells. Moreover, the renal tubules of group III treated with eugenol showed focal affection (Fig 3e; treated with eugenol around 150 mg/kg/day). They seemed flattened in some places and inflated and vacuolated in others. Pyknotic nuclei dominated most of the afflicted tubules. Inside the deteriorated tubules were extruded cells and intraluminal cellular debris. And some renal corpuscles have enlarged capsular gaps. In the afflicted locations, there was moderate peritubular cellular infiltration (Fig 3f).

Group V of Wistar albino rats that were administered dimethoate exhibited a significant level of cortical affection. Thyroidization was observed in the cortical tissue. Numerous convoluted tubules exhibited irregular dilation accompanied by a flattened epithelial lining. The lumina were saturated with hyaline substance. Diverse levels of degeneration were observed in additional convoluted tubules, spanning from pyknotic nuclei and vacuolated cell lining to complete cell extrusion within the lumen. Detailed peritubular cellular infiltration was observed in every sample that was analysed (Fig. 5a-c).

Fig 3:- Kidney tissue sample stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) stain.

Fig 3 (a–e): Renal sections stained with H&E; (a) 100X magnification of the renal cortex of control albino rats showing typical cortical tissue structure with well identified renal corpuscles (R), proximal (P) and distal (D) convoluted tubules. (b) Control rats section 400X magnification. (c, d) Group II section staining at 400X magnification; only one vehicle with almost normal structure was obtained. Renal corpuscle, P: Proximal Convoluted Tubule, D: Distal Convoluted Tubule. (e) 400X magnification of peritubular (*) and pericorpuscular (#) cellular infiltration in a renal cortex segment of group III rats given eugenol at 150 mg/kg/day. Degenerated cells are found in few tubules (**); P is the proximal convoluted tubule; R is the renal corpuscle. (e) Variable degrees of tubular affection seen in the 400X magnification renal cortex of group V under subacute confinement and eugenol. Some tubular cells show up as enlarged, vacuolated cells with intraluminal extruded cells and pyknotic nuclei (*). The intraluminal cellular debris seems to have flattened other tubular cells (#). A renal corpuscle (R) demonstrates expanded corpuscular space. Moreover observed is moderate peritubular cellular infiltration (**). Group IV has not changed all that much.

Fig 4:- Kidney tissue sample of treated with Stress induced stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) stain.

G V- TS-150mg-kidney-10x-

G V- TS-150mg-kidney-40x-

Fig 4(a-c): H&E stain of renal cortex from rats in group V, treated with eugenol at a dosage of 150mg/kg/day. (a) Image at 100X magnification displaying thyroidization of the renal cortex. Multiple intricate tubules exhibit irregularity, dilation, and a flattened epithelial lining. Several of them exhibit intraluminal hyalinized material (↑↑), accompanied by a significant cellular infiltration (^) in the intervening spaces. (b) At a magnification of 400X, there is a clear visual of a renal tubule that is much enlarged. The inner lining of the tubule consists of flattened cells, and it is packed with material that has become hyalinized (*). Other cells are surrounded by vacuolated swelling cells with condensed nuclei (↑). (c) At a magnification of 400X, the image reveals badly deteriorated tubules with the expulsion of their lining cells into the inner space (A).

Additionally, there is a significant presence of mononuclear cells around the tubules (↑↑) and an enlargement of the space surrounding the kidney capsule (S).

Fig 5:- Brain tissue sample with Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) stain.

Fig 5: The molecular (M), Purkinje cell (P), and granular cell layers (G) are displayed in sections (a,b) of a control rat. (Hematoxylin and eosin staining, magnification $\times 10$; Scale bar = 100 μm). There is a single row of Purkinje cells (P). Observe flask-shaped Purkinje cells characterised by upwardly extending apical dendrites (c,d) (coloured yellow), lightly pigmented nuclei, and conspicuous nucleoli. The granular layer is composed of densely packed spherical granule cells with pale vesicular nuclei, as indicated by the black arrow. The molecular layer (M) has a significant presence of glial cells and the intervals between cerebellar islands (*). (Hematoxylin and eosin staining. Magnification of 20x and 40x; Scale bar = 50 micrometres).

Fig 6:- Brain tissue sample of treated with Stress induced stained (Group – V Treated with Stress – TS- 150mg/kg/day) with Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) stain.

Fig 6 indicates the effects of stress on Wistar albino rats treated with group V. The cerebellum cells of the treated group of rats exhibit varying degrees of damaging alterations in both intensity and distribution (A). (B) Some Purkinje cells exhibit cytoplasm that has been evenly mixed and faint nuclei that are highly elevated. Observe the presence of vacuolation in the adjacent molecular layer (shown by a thick arrow). Granular layers exhibit interstices. (C) The image was taken at higher magnification using H&E staining. The magnification used was A $\times$ 20 for image A and B $\times$ 40 for image B. The scale bar in the image represents a length of 50 μ m.

D. HEMATOXYLIN AND EOSIN STAINING OF THE BRAIN

The histological examination of the cerebellar cortex sections from the control group rats demonstrated the presence of three successive layers. Fig 6 A shows that the molecular layer was located on the outer side, followed by the layer of Purkinje cells, while the granular layer was situated on the inner side. The Purkinje cells had a flask-shaped morphology, characterised by the presence of apical dendrites. They were arranged in a single line. The features of this were a light-staining cytoplasm and a nucleus with a central clear space. The granular cell layer exhibited densely clustered granule cells and cerebellar islands (Fig 6 B,C).

Sample of brain tissue from the stress-induced group V (treated with stress; TS: 150 mg/kg/day) was stained. Upon examination of stained sections with Hematoxylin, it was shown that the cerebellum cells of the treatment group of rats were much more impacted compared to the control group. Observed were Purkinje cells displaying degeneration, characterised by intensely discoloured cytoplasm and nuclei. In addition, halos were detected in the vacant areas surrounding deteriorated Purkinje cells.

In contrast, the cells in the granular layer exhibited a nearly normal state, with slight gaps observed between them (Fig 6 A, B, & C).

IV. DISCUSSION

Medicinal herbs are essential in traditional medicinal practices globally. A significant proportion of the population in developing nations continues to rely on these countries for their healthcare needs. Eugenol is a component found in numerous therapeutic herbs and has been documented to have multiple properties. In the field of traditional medicine, this remedy is employed to combat gastrointestinal diseases such as flatulence and chronic diarrhoea. Furthermore, a study has demonstrated its efficacy in treating vaginal candidiasis.[17]

The histological structure of the liver and kidney of rats that were administered eugenol or cinnamic aldehyde appeared to be almost normal upon evaluation. The present studies did not show any histopathological consequences of cinnamic aldehyde on laboratory wistar albino rats, despite its documented larvicidal effectiveness against mosquitoes[18] and insecticidal activity

against American cockroaches.[10] Gautam and Goel discovered that the histological examinations of the liver, spleen, kidney, heart, and testis/ovary showed no signs of pathological alterations even when a greater dosage of 800 mg of *ocimum sanctum* extract (OSE) was supplied for a duration of 28 days.[19]

The present findings support the initial assessment by the National Toxicology Programme, which demonstrated no signs of toxicity or carcinogenicity associated with this essential oil. [20] In addition, Xuesen et al. found that there were no indications of Flavokawain A (FKA) - induced toxicity in the liver, kidney, colon, lung, heart, spleen, and thymus of male wistar albino rats.[21] This was observed after the wistar albino rats were fed with either an AIN-76A diet or an AIN-76A diet supplemented with 0.6% (6 g/kg food) FKA or 0.6% commercial kava root extract (KRE) for a duration of three weeks. In contrast, Metero et al. [22] shown that large dosages of cinnamaldehyde caused genetic changes at the chromosomal level. They also proposed that the liver was the primary organ affected by these negative effects.

The microscopic examination of the livers and kidneys of wistar albino rats exposed to eugenol and other essential oils showed a histological structure that aligns with the findings of the National Toxicology Programme.[23] Additionally, this study found an increased presence of Von Kupffer cells in the livers, as well as mononuclear cellular infiltration in the peritubular and pericorpuscular regions of the kidneys. Earlier, it was proposed that the administration of eugenol could potentially enhance the production of prostaglandins, which play a crucial role in inflammation, apoptosis, and cellular growth mechanisms.[24]

There exist multiple conflicting accounts concerning the potential effects of eugenol on the health of both humans and animals. As an illustration, the present investigation failed to identify any noteworthy histopathological impacts of eugenol on the structure of the liver and kidneys. On rare occasions, examination of the livers and kidneys of mice that were treated revealed mild degenerative alterations. Nevertheless, methyleugenol and isoeugenol, which are eugenol derivatives, have been documented to have hepatotoxic, nephrotoxic, and carcinogenic effects.[25][26] Furthermore, leukocyte migration suggested that eugenol rich fraction (ERF) impeded the development of cirrhosis and the progression of liver fibrosis by mitigating

oxidative stress and inhibiting inflammation (Shakir Ali et al.).[27] Furthermore, in cholestatic liver disease, eugenol has a promising influence on liver histology, according to Sarikaya. [28] Additionally, Janes et al.[29] documented a case of hepatic failure in a 15-month-old child subsequent to ingesting 10 ml of clove oil containing methyleugenol, isoeugenol, and eugenol.

Furthermore, hepatotoxicity may be induced by a vinyllogous quinone methide produced by the metabolic oxidation of eugenol, according to Mizutani et al. [30] According to Usta et al. [31] respectively, the mitochondria are the intended site of eugenol's action, which disrupts mitochondrial functions specifically at proton transfer sites. Conversely, several studies have proposed that eugenol may serve as a protective agent against hepatotoxicity induced by chemicals. Eugenol was characterised as a hepatoprotective agent against carbon tetrachloride-induced toxicity by Raghuramulu and Krishnaswamy.[32] Eugenol's antiperoxidative activity and inhibition of liver microsomal monooxygenase activities, in addition to its function in reducing O₂ formation, contribute to this protective effect.[33] Furthermore, Hong et al.[34] Reached the conclusion that pretreatment of rodents with eugenol completely protected them from the nephrotoxicity of the agricultural fungicide N-(3, 5-dichlorophenyl) succinimide.

V. CONCLUSION

With the exception of the renal cortex, brain, and liver, the examined essential oils exhibited negligible detrimental effects on Wistar albino female rats. However, rats administered 150 mg/kg/day of eugenol in combination with subacute restraint developed notable hepatotoxic and nephrotoxic effects, but no discernible impact on brain tissue. Further investigation is required to encompass a larger sample of animals and to investigate other variables such as gender disparities, duration of exposure, varying levels of dosage, blood composition, and other specific biochemical targets prior to rendering any recommendations about the use of these chemicals as insecticides.

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REFERENCES

1. Kadum Yakob H, Manaf Uyub A, Fariza Sulaiman S. Toxicological evaluation of 80% methanol extract of *Ludwigia octovalvis* (Jacq.) P.H. Raven leaves (Onagraceae) in BALB/c mice. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 2012;142(3):663–8.
2. WHO. WHO guidelines on safety monitoring of herbal medicines in pharmacovigilance systems. World Heal Organ Geneva. 2004;82.
3. Bakkali F, Averbeck S, Averbeck D. ScienceDirect.com - Food and Chemical Toxicology - Biological effects of essential oils – A review. *Food Chem ...* [Internet]. 2008; Available from: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0278691507004541%5Cnpapers2://publication/uuid/6990C644-401E-450A-A8BA-71421ACAFD18>
4. Edris AE. Pharmaceutical and therapeutic potentials of essential oils and their individual volatile constituents: A review. Vol. 21, *Phytotherapy Research.* 2007. p. 308–23.
5. Amr E. Edris. Pharmaceutical and Therapeutic Potentials of Essential Oils and Their Individual Volatile Constituents: *Phyther Res* [Internet]. 2008;22(4):544–549. Available from: <http://www3.interscience.wiley.com/journal/117934759/abstract>
6. Yim VWC, Ng AKY, Tsang HWH, Leung AY. A review on the effects of aromatherapy for patients with depressive symptoms. Vol. 15, *Journal of Alternative and Complementary Medicine.* 2009. p. 187–95.
7. Abadio AKR, Kioshima ES, Martins NF, Maigret B, Felipe MSS, Freitas SM, et al. A pharmacophore-based virtual screening approach for the discovery of *Trypanosoma cruzi* GAPDH inhibitors (vol 5, pg 2019, 2013). *J Chem Inf Model.* 2015;
8. Schmid R, Bruneton J, Hatton CK. *Pharmacognosy, Phytochemistry, Medicinal Plants.* *Taxon.* 1995;44(3):469.
9. Ernst E. *Pharmacognosy: Phytochemistry, Medicinal Plants.* *Focus Altern Complement Ther.* 2000;5(2):157–8.
10. Enan E. Insecticidal activity of essential oils: Octopaminergic sites of action. *Comp Biochem Physiol - C Toxicol Pharmacol.* 2001;130(3):325–37.
11. Abou El Ela N, Enan E. Insecticidal Activity of some Essential Oils: CAMP Mediates Effect. *J High Inst Public Heal.* 2001;31(1):15–30.
12. Sawamura M, Sun SH, Ozaki K, Ishikawa J, Ukeda H. Inhibitory effects of citrus essential oils and their components on the formation of N-nitrosodimethylamine. *J Agric Food Chem.* 1999;47(12):4868–72.
13. Singh G, Maurya S, deLampasona MP, Catalan CAN. A comparison of chemical, antioxidant and antimicrobial studies of cinnamon leaf and bark volatile oils, oleoresins and their constituents. *Food Chem Toxicol.* 2007;45(9):1650–61.
14. Coats JR. Mechanisms of Toxic Action and Structure-Activity Relationships for Organochlorine and Synthetic Pyrethroid Insecticides. *Environ Health Perspect.* 1990;87:255.
15. Miyazawa M, Watanabe H, Kameoka H. Inhibition of Acetylcholinesterase Activity by Monoterpenoids with a p-Menthane Skeleton. *J Agric Food Chem.* 1997;45(3):677–9.

16. Singh DK, Verma R. Spectrophotometric determination of corticosteroids and its application in pharmaceutical formulation. *Iran J Pharmacol Ther.* 2008;7(1):61–5.
17. Selvan P, Malathi, Rajan R. Effect of 4-allyl-2-methoxyphenol (eugenol) on motor co-ordination in subacute restraint stress induced wistar albino rats. *J Appl Pharm Sci.* 2016;6(11):120–5.
18. Cheng SS, Liu JY, Tsai KH, Chen WJ, Chang ST. Chemical composition and mosquito larvicidal activity of essential oils from leaves of different *Cinnamomum osmophloeum* provenances. *J Agric Food Chem.* 2004;52(14):4395–400.
19. Gautam MK, Goel RK. Toxicological study of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn leaves: Hematological, biochemical, and histopathological studies. *J Toxicol.* 2014;2014.
20. NTP toxicology and carcinogenesis studies of trans-cinnamaldehyde (CAS No. 14371-10-9) in F344/N rats and B6C3F1 mice (feed studies). *Natl Toxicol Program Tech Rep Ser.* 2004;(514):1–281.
21. Li X, Xu X, Ji T, Liu Z, Gu M, Hoang BH, et al. Dietary feeding of flavokawain A, a Kava chalcone, exhibits a satisfactory safety profile and its association with enhancement of phase II enzymes in mice. *Toxicol Reports.* 2014;1:2–11.
22. Mereto E, Brambilla-Campart G, Ghia M, Martelli A, Brambilla G. Cinnamaldehyde-induced micronuclei in rodent liver. *Mutat Res Toxicol.* 1994;322(1):1–8.
23. National Toxicology Program. NTP Toxicology and Carcinogenesis Studies of Benzyl Alcohol (CAS No. 100-51-6) in F344/N Rats and B6C3F1 Mice (Gavage Studies). *Natl Toxicol Program Tech Rep Ser* [Internet]. 1989;343:1–158. Available from: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12724782>
24. Martínez B, Pérez-Castillo A, Santos A. The mitochondrial respiratory complex I is a target for 15-deoxy- Δ 12,14-prostaglandin J2 action. *J Lipid Res.* 2005;46(4):736–43.
25. NTP. NTP Technical Report on the Toxicology and Carcinogenesis Studies of Perfluorooctanoic Acid. 2020;(May).
26. Abdo KM, Blumenthal GM, Bridge DA, Bucher JR, Chapin RE, Haseman JK, et al. NTP TECHNICAL REPORT ON THE TOXICOLOGY AND CARCINOGENESIS STUDIES OF METHYLEUGENOL (CAS NO. 93-15-2) IN F344/N RATS AND B6C3F1 MICE (GAVAGE STUDIES). Vol. TR-491, NTP Technical Report on the Toxicology and Carcinogenesis Studies Series. 2000. p. 1–420.
27. Ali S, Prasad R, Mahmood A, Routray I, Shinkafi TS, Sahin K, et al. Eugenol-rich Fraction of *Syzygium aromaticum* (Clove) Reverses Biochemical and Histopathological Changes in Liver Cirrhosis and Inhibits Hepatic Cell Proliferation. *J Cancer Prev.* 2014;19(4):288–300.
28. Sarikaya M, Filik L, Ergul B, Dogan Z, Alparslan Gonultas M, Hucumenoglu S, et al. Favourable effect of Eugenol on liver histology in acute cholestasis in rats after bile duct ligation. *Bratislava Med J.* 2014;115(10):622–4.
29. Janes SEJ, Price CSG, Thomas D. Essential oil poisoning: N-acetylcysteine for eugenol-induced hepatic failure and analysis of a national database. *Eur J Pediatr.* 2005;164(8):520–2.

30. Mizutani T, Satoh K, Nomura H. Hepatotoxicity of eugenol and related compounds in mice depleted of glutathione: Structural requirements for toxic potency. *Res Commun Chem Pathol Pharmacol.* 1991;73(1):87–96.
31. Usta J, Kreydiyyeh S, Bajakian K, Nakkash-Chmaisse H. In vitro effect of eugenol and cinnamaldehyde on membrane potential and respiratory chain complexes in isolated rat liver mitochondria. *Food Chem Toxicol.* 2002;40(7):935–40.
32. Krishnaswamy K, Raghuramulu N. Bioactive phytochemicals with emphasis on dietary practices. *Indian J Med Res.* 1998;108(NOV.):167–81.
33. Chericoni S, Prieto JM, Iacopini P, Cioni P, Morelli I. In vitro activity of the essential oil of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* and eugenol in peroxynitrite-induced oxidative processes. *J Agric Food Chem.* 2005;53(12):4762–5.
34. Hong SK, Anestis DK, Brown PI, Rankin GO. Effect of glucuronidation substrates/inhibitors on N-(3,5-dichlorophenyl)succinimidenephrotoxicity in Fischer 344 rats. *Toxicology.* 1999;132(1):43–55.

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